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A Creative Folio

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The Colors That Endure

The broken bits of crayons, dull and small,
Lay silent once, but now they shine for all.
From scattered hues that time had cast away,
New light emerged, a brighter, kinder day.

With patient hands and warmth to guide the flame,
Each color melted, yet remained the same.
Though broken once, their beauty reappears,
A blend of joy, of hope, of dreams, of tears.

So too are we, though different in our ways,
Each soul a shade that lights another's days.
When joined as one, our colors intertwine,
And in our unity, all hues align.

See crimson's glow of passion, love, and might,
Yet temper it, for anger dims its light.
While azure whispers calm, serene, and deep,
A vow of peace our restless hearts shall keep.

Bright yellow laughs with joy and childlike grace,
Though sorrow hides behind its shining face.
And green renews, where faith and growth reside,
Where hope and peace in gentle hearts abide.

Pure white reflects the soul's unsullied part,
Of innocence and truth within the heart.
And brown, the tone of earth and humble hand,
Speaks steadfast care that time shall not disband.

Majestic purple dreams in mystic hue,
Where wisdom stirs and visions still pursue.
While orange burns with courage, joy, and cheer,
It fuels the heart when weary days draw near.

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In black, both strength and silence intertwine,
A mark of power, grace, and grand design.
Though death may wear its somber, quiet shade,
New life through darkened paths is often made.

Thus every hue, though broken, bruised, or torn,
Becomes more bright through trials it has borne.
For in each soul, the light of love is pure,
The colors blend and ever shall endure.